

**ILMIY VA
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AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 3 (Май-Июнь)

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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SOMATIC COMORBIDITY AND CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA MARKERS IN WOMEN WITH PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE

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Abstract. Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) is a multifactorial condition in which systemic connective tissue weakness is regarded as a central pathogenetic element. This study analyzed the somatic comorbidity profile of women with POP, with particular attention to conditions that act as clinical markers of connective tissue dysplasia. A retrospective analysis was performed of 401 women treated for POP at the Department of Operative Gynecology of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Maternal and Child Health (2019–2023). The leading comorbidities were iron-deficiency anemia (53.6 %), lower-limb varicose veins (45.1 %), urolithiasis (34.7 %), arterial hypertension (25.9 %), and diffuse goiter (21.7 %). Conditions associated with connective tissue dysplasia — varicose veins, abdominal-wall hernias (3.0 %), and hemorrhoids (3.5 %) — were well represented, and in the prospective comparison groups the prevalence of varicose veins reached 34–48 %. The predominance of vascular, metabolic, and connective-tissue disorders confirms the multifactorial, connective-tissue–related pathogenesis of POP and underscores the need for comprehensive preoperative assessment and an individualized choice of surgical tactics, especially because connective tissue dysplasia predisposes to failure of native-tissue repair and to recurrence.

Keywords: pelvic organ prolapse, connective tissue dysplasia, somatic comorbidity, varicose veins, risk factors, recurrence.

СОМАТИЧЕСКАЯ КОМОРБИДНОСТЬ И МАРКЁРЫ ДИСПЛАЗИИ СОЕДИНИТЕЛЬНОЙ ТКАНИ У ЖЕНЩИН С ПРОЛАПСОМ ТАЗОВЫХ ОРГАНОВ

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Аннотация. Проплапс тазовых органов (ПТО) — мультифакторное заболевание, в патогенезе которого системная слабость соединительной ткани рассматривается как одно из центральных звеньев. В работе проанализирован профиль соматической коморбидности у женщин с ПТО с особым вниманием к состояниям, выступающим клиническими маркёрами дисплазии соединительной ткани. Проведён ретроспективный анализ 401 женщины, проходившей лечение по поводу ПТО в отделении оперативной гинекологии Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра здоровья матери и ребёнка (2019–2023). Ведущими сопутствующими заболеваниями были железодефицитная анемия (53,6 %), варикозное расширение вен нижних конечностей (45,1 %), мочекаменная болезнь (34,7 %), артериальная гипертензия (25,9 %) и диффузный зоб (21,7 %). Состояния, ассоциированные с дисплазией соединительной ткани, — варикозная болезнь, грыжи передней брюшной стенки (3,0 %) и геморрой (3,5 %) — были хорошо представлены, а в проспективных группах сравнения частота варикоза достигала 34–48 %. Преобладание сосудистых, метаболических и соединительнотканых нарушений подтверждает мультифакторный, связанный с соединительной тканью патогенез ПТО и подчёркивает необходимость комплексного предоперационного обследования и индивидуального выбора хирургической тактики, тем более что дисплазия соединительной ткани

предрасполагает к несостоятельности пластики собственными тканями и к рецидиву.

Ключевые слова: пролапс тазовых органов, дисплазия соединительной ткани, соматическая коморбидность, варикозная болезнь, факторы риска, рецидив.

ЧАНОҚ АЪЗОЛАРИ ПРОЛАПСИ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН АЁЛЛАРДА СОМАТИК КОМОРБИДЛИК ВА БИРИКТИРУВЧИ ТЎҚИМА ДИСПЛАЗИЯСИ МАРКЕРЛАРИ

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Аннотация. Чаноқ аъзолари пролапси (ЧАП) — кўп омилли касаллик бўлиб, унинг патогенезида бириктирувчи тўқиманинг тизимли заифлиги марказий бўғинлардан бири сифатида қаралади. Ишда ЧАП билан оғриган аёлларнинг соматик коморбидлик профили, айниқса бириктирувчи тўқима дисплазиясининг клиник маркерлари бўлиб хизмат қилувчи ҳолатларга алоҳида эътибор қаратилган ҳолда таҳлил қилинган. Республика ихтисослаштирилган она ва бола саломатлиги илмий-амалий тиббиёт маркази оператив гинекология бўлимида ЧАП юзасидан даволанган 401 нафар аёл ретроспектив таҳлил қилинди. Етакчи ҳамроҳ касалликлар темир танқислиги анемияси (53,6 %), қуйи оёқ томирлари варикоз кенгайиши (45,1 %), сийдик-тош касаллиги (34,7 %), артериал гипертензия (25,9 %) ва диффуз букоқ (21,7 %) бўлди. Бириктирувчи тўқима дисплазияси билан боғлиқ ҳолатлар — варикоз касаллиги, қорин олди девори чурралари (3,0 %) ва бавосил (3,5 %) — яхши намоён бўлди, проспектив қиёслаш гуруҳларида эса варикоз тарқалганлиги 34–48 % га етди. Томир, метаболик ва бириктирувчи тўқима бузилишларининг

устунлиги ЧАПнинг кўп омилли, бириктирувчи тўқима билан боғлиқ патогенезини тасдиқлайди ва пухта операциядан олдинги текширув ҳамда жарроҳлик тактикасини индивидуал танлаш зарурлигини таъкидлайди, айниқса бириктирувчи тўқима дисплазияси ўз тўқималари билан пластиканинг етишмовчилигига ва қайталанишга мойиллик яратади.

Калит сўзлар: чанок аъзолари пролапси, бириктирувчи тўқима дисплазияси, соматик коморбидлик, варикоз касаллиги, хавф омиллари, қайталаниш.

Introduction. Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) results from a polyetiological anatomical and functional failure of the pelvic-floor support structures. Although childbirth and ageing are well-recognized contributors, defects of the connective tissue are increasingly viewed as the central pathogenetic substrate. In connective tissue dysplasia, an atypical spatial structure of type I and III collagen, its partial replacement by type IV collagen, and disturbances of elastin reduce the mechanical strength of the ligaments and fasciae that support the pelvic organs, predisposing to prolapse even in women with few obstetric risk factors. Because connective tissue dysplasia is a systemic disorder, it manifests not only in the pelvic floor but also in other organ systems, producing characteristic comorbidities such as varicose veins, hernias of various locations, and joint hypermobility.

The systemic nature of this process implies that the somatic comorbidity profile of women with POP should reflect an underlying connective-tissue weakness. Characterizing this profile is clinically relevant, because connective tissue dysplasia predisposes to failure of native-tissue repair and to recurrence, and its recognition can inform preoperative assessment and the choice of surgical tactics. The aim of this study was to analyze the somatic comorbidity profile of women with POP, with particular attention to conditions that serve as clinical markers of connective tissue dysplasia.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis was performed of 401 women treated for pelvic organ prolapse at the Department of Operative Gynecology of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Maternal and Child Health between 2019 and 2023. All patients underwent a clinical-somatic examination, a gynecological examination, and pelvic ultrasonography. Concomitant somatic diseases were recorded and analyzed, with emphasis on conditions associated with connective tissue dysplasia (lower-limb varicose veins, abdominal-wall hernias, hemorrhoids). The distribution of comorbidities is presented in Table 1. For comparison, the prevalence of selected comorbidities in the prospectively followed surgical groups was also examined; categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Table 1.

Somatic comorbidity in women with pelvic organ prolapse (n = 401)

Comorbidity	n	%
Iron-deficiency anemia	215	53.62
Lower-limb varicose veins	181	45.14
Urolithiasis	139	34.66
Arterial hypertension	104	25.94
Diffuse goiter	87	21.70
Other cardiovascular pathology	65	16.21
Burdened allergic history	36	8.98
Autoimmune diseases	27	6.73
Hemorrhoids	14	3.49
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	13	3.24
Abdominal-wall hernias	12	2.99
Chronic tonsillitis	3	0.75

Results. The studied cohort showed a high burden of somatic comorbidity. The most frequent condition was iron-deficiency anemia, present in 215 women (53.6 %), followed by lower-limb varicose veins in 181 women (45.1 %). Urolithiasis was diagnosed in 139 patients (34.7 %), which may reflect regional features of water–salt metabolism. Arterial hypertension was present in 104 women (25.9 %) and other forms of cardiovascular pathology in 65 (16.2 %). Among endocrine disorders, diffuse goiter was found in 87 patients (21.7 %), consistent with the known prevalence of iodine deficiency in the region. Autoimmune diseases were recorded in 27 women (6.7 %) and a burdened allergic history in 36 (9.0 %). Less common comorbidities included hemorrhoids (3.5 %), type 2 diabetes mellitus (3.2 %), abdominal-wall hernias (3.0 %), and chronic tonsillitis (0.8 %).

Several of these conditions are recognized clinical markers of connective tissue dysplasia. Lower-limb varicose veins (45.1 %), abdominal-wall hernias (3.0 %), and hemorrhoids (3.5 %) all reflect a systemic weakness of connective tissue and act as indirect indicators of the same substrate that underlies the failure of pelvic-floor support. The high prevalence of varicose veins in particular points to the contribution of connective tissue dysplasia to the pathogenesis of POP.

This pattern was reinforced in the prospectively followed surgical groups. Lower-limb varicose veins were present in 34.2 % to 48.4 % of patients ($p = 0.028$ between groups), iron-deficiency anemia in 8.2 % to 34.2 % ($p < 0.0001$), and hemorrhoids together with diffuse goiter in up to 13.8 % ($p < 0.0001$). In these cohorts, the leading positions in the comorbidity structure were occupied by diseases linked to systemic connective-tissue weakness and venous stasis, while the obstetric history was predominantly burdened by the sequelae of birth trauma, such as cicatricial deformities of the perineum and cervix.

Conclusion. Women with pelvic organ prolapse carry a high burden of somatic comorbidity, in which vascular, metabolic, and connective-tissue disorders

predominate. The frequent occurrence of varicose veins, hernias, and other conditions associated with connective tissue dysplasia supports the view that POP is a multifactorial disorder with a connective-tissue substrate at its core. Recognition of these clinical markers is important in practice: it argues for a comprehensive preoperative assessment of the somatic background and for an individualized choice of surgical tactics, particularly because connective tissue dysplasia predisposes to failure of native-tissue repair and to recurrence. Incorporating the comorbidity profile into preoperative planning may help to identify patients at higher risk of recurrence and to guide reinforcement of the repair.

References

1. Bump R.C., Mattiasson A., Bø K., et al. The standardization of terminology of female pelvic organ prolapse and pelvic floor dysfunction. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 1996;175(1):10–17.
2. Jelovsek J.E., Maher C., Barber M.D. Pelvic organ prolapse. *Lancet.* 2021;398(10294):1027–1038.
3. Schulten S.F.M., Claas-Quax M.J., Weemhoff M., et al. Risk factors for primary pelvic organ prolapse and prolapse recurrence: an updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2022;227(2):192–208.
4. Vergeldt T.F.M., Weemhoff M., IntHout J., Kluivers K.B. Risk factors for pelvic organ prolapse and its recurrence: a systematic review. *Int Urogynecol J.* 2015;26(11):1559–1573.
5. Friedman T., Eslick G.D., Dietz H.P. Risk factors for prolapse recurrence: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int Urogynecol J.* 2018;29(1):13–21.
6. Allen-Brady K., Norton P.A., Hill A.J., Rowe K., Cannon-Albright L.A. Risk of pelvic organ prolapse treatment based on extended family history. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2020;223(1):1051–1058.
7. DeLancey J.O.L. What's new in the functional anatomy of pelvic organ prolapse? *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol.* 2016;28(5):420–429.

8. Yuldashev S.K. Laparoscopic native tissue repair for post-hysterectomy apical prolapse: a prospective comparative study of clinical outcomes and safety. *American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*. 2025;15(9):3187–3191.
9. Yuldashev S.K. Autologous reconstruction of central anterior vaginal wall defects: a mesh-free surgical technique. *American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*. 2025;15(11):3964–3966.